

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF APHORISMS WITH THE CONCEPT OF
EDUCATION AND SCIENCE (IN THE EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES)

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Annotation: The main feature of aphorisms is a brief artistic expression of a wise, typical thought in which expression, not image, is the leader of meaning. One in the article on the other hand, interest in studying the syntactic features of aphorisms in speech on the other hand, semantics in the speech of English and Uzbek languages characteristics have been thoroughly analyzed. The purpose of the study is to generalize ideas of the pragmatic qualification of aphorism as a verbal means of expression aspects and differential features of reality in the form of a phrase (phrase text). Identify and describe universal generalizations.

Key words: Aphorism, English aphorisms, Uzbek aphorisms, culture, special factors, concepts of time.

Introduction : Aphorisms are general truths about life, human behavior, or the world or are concise and often intelligent statements that convey an understanding. They are usually short, memorable and full of wisdom. Aphorisms are often used to give guidance, offer a different perspective, or make a short and memorable point used to wake up. They have been in literature, philosophy and everyday life for centuries has been a popular form of expression in conversation. As you know, in English and Uzbek languages .Describing and classifying aphorisms is also important. The term "aphorism" derived from the Greek "(aphorismos - "a short phrase containing a general truth"). Aphoristic phrases are quoted in writing as well as in our everyday speech. Then the existence of truth makes them universally accepted. Contrary to proverbs, wise the origin of words is attributed to a specific person (writer, poet, publicist, philosopher, scientist, statesman, etc.) are relevant and retain their identity. Representing achievements and losses in human life in English and Uzbek languages It is very interesting to understand that there are many aphorisms. Therefore, they are linguists has become a linguistic phenomenon that researchers cannot ignore.

Main Part. In today's modern linguistics the anthropocentric direction, the view of the human factor as an important phenomenon in the study of language, is growing. The linguocognitive, linguopragmatic and linguoculturological aspects of language units are widely studied on the basis of this direction. One of the main problem to be studied in cognitive linguistics is concept and according to acknowledgement of many researcher's cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology are leading areas of the anthropocentric paradigm. If cognitive linguistics is a science that studies the nature of a particular concept in the linguistic image of the world and its relation to world realities, the concept is one of the leading categories of cognitive linguistics and is an element of communication between culture and humanity. Although the term "concept" has been widely used in linguistics since the 1990s, it still does not have a single explanation or interpretation. Professor G. M. Hoshimov describes the concept as follows: "A concept is the result of not only two important processes, conceptualization and categorization, which are closely related to each other, but also it is an end result of a number of other important processes (such as psychologization, cognition, sociology, (linguo) semantization,

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sociolectization, stylization (like dialectization, variantization, and idiolectization), and it constitutes the cognitive basis of the linguistic semantics as a holistic conceptual/cognitive semantics". As a consequence of considering the aforementioned notions, we may conclude that the concept is the end product of various processes occurring in our thoughts, and it is a unit that necessitates further research in cognitive linguistics. At this point, we'd like to concentrate on the notion of "wedding" in English and Uzbek, two unrelated languages. Many aphorisms in English and Uzbek languages researchers conducted research. For English aphorisms, see Taylor, Ridout and Many scholars such as Whiting, Norrick, Collis, Galperin and others are great in this field contributed. However, due to different approaches and objectives, their publications focus on one aspect or another of the aphorisms. In general. In short, these linguists theorize how we learn to use language provides an overview of the basics. From the point of view of Uzbek aphorism studies, Some thorough works related to aphorisms contribute to the knowledge of this field added, and in this regard, the difference between phrases and aphorisms is two criteria: content and grammatical structures, aphorisms collected and collected by authors based on which it is mentioned. Here we are primarily research methods, sampling, data related to data collection, data analysis, instrumentation. Procedure for conducting research are also presented at the same time. Accuracy and reliability in this study is stated and substantiated. In general, in English and Uzbek The studied aphorisms are composed in simple, compound, complex and comparative sentences. As for complex sentences, English and Uzbek aphorisms are second in percentage is in place. In terms of comparative sentences, English and Uzbek aphorisms are the lowest was found to have a percentage. Comparative sentences in English and Uzbek languages. As far as the data are concerned, the difference between Eq comparison is more commonly used. As for compound sentences, the number of compound aphorisms in English is the same as in Uzbek much less than the joint Aphorism. Moreover, English is synthetic. Aphorism in the form of coordination than in the form of synthetic coordination there are more aphorisms, only compound sentences without a coordinator in Uzbek examples 98 aphorisms make up 100% and Uzbek in coordinating clauses an aphorism cannot be formed.

Of course, one should take into account here the specifics of the English-speaking way of life, which manifests itself in an increase in the value status of people of respectable age in society. This is convincingly evidenced by such signals in the English-speaking society as:

- appearance of the word middlescence –the period of life between 40 and 65;
- softening in everyday vocabulary communication age discrimination [from 65 years and on]: great age; honorable age; autumn years; golden age; golden years; advanced age; ripe age; the value of years; age of seniority; the vintage years; third age [3];
- it is considered undesirable to use the word old, which indicates person's age; it is replaced by multi-component phrases - euphemisms with a positive connotation: woman of certain age; September people; nature lady; retired people; white top; experientially enhanced person; seasoned man; chronologically gifted; middleaged man; venerable man; nature American; people of the "third age"; third age; golden age; a man in years; senior citizen advanced in age person; advanced adult, etc.

This feature of English-speaking culture should certainly be taken into account in linguodidactic perception Uzbek-speaking environment. Uzbek-English idiomatic the similarity is widely revealed by the most various semantic collections. Wed parallelism of Uzbek-English USK expressing semantic-figurative proximity of the dominant "young" [specifically "youth" /

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“inexperience” / “lack of life experience”]: yoshlik – beboshlik – Salad days [resp. Russian "milk on the lips not dry", "young-green", i.e. in general, “it’s time for life’s inexperience”] followed by a deepening into the Uzbek idiomatic diversity.

Uzbek-English comparison is determined by the dependence on the mentality of the carriers of the corresponding language, provides for taking into account methods thinking [concreteness - abstractness], formed in compared cultures of relations to one or another linguo-philosophical category, features of communicative behavior and etc. When represented in languages, they intersect, forming the general and distinctive in the system of reflection specifically a selected fragment of the picture of the world. Progressive assimilation of the English language by the Uzbek-speaking society led to close attention to broad typological problems and the theory of linguistic universals. This not only solves the current linguistic tasks, but also done forecasts for the future Uzbek-English comparative comparisons, removing difficulties in Uzbeks learning English in based on new pedagogical technologies.

These examples are only one of a large collection of aphorisms in English and Uzbek languages is a part of Each aphorism deals with different aspects of life, human nature and providing brief and memorable insights into cultural values covers a specific topic or message. There are many English and Uzbek aphorisms in literature. In literature many aphorisms that are used have lost their literary use and appeared besides the work, it remains relevant in its meaning. Shakespeare in his works used aphorisms. The use of many aphorisms is his keen insight and indicates his judgment. Here are some examples: Having nothing, nothing can he lose. (Henry VI) Life is a tale told by an idiot-full of sound and fury, meaning nothing. (Macbeth) Lord, what fools these mortals be! (A Midsummer Night's Dream) Wise words in independent scientific genres, scientific, philosophical, historical, artistic can also be found in works. Sometimes the work is Wise from beginning to end may consist of words (Farobi). Some works of Alisher Navoi rich in wise words ("Nazm ul-jawahir", "Arbain", "Mahbub ul-qulub" and others). He is wise in the literature of Eastern peoples, including Uzbek literature most of the words are found in the form of advice and rebuke. In Uzbek: Open the truth, follow the right path. (Abu Ali ibn Sina) .Wise words close to the living language and folk proverbs are also widespread. In Uzbek: "A soldier without a bullet is a sheath without a sword" (Oybek) "You can't chew soup for a teething child" (A. Qahhor) Among Uzbek writers, Hamza, A. Qadiri, G. Ghulam, Oybek, H. Olimjon, A. Qahhor, Shaikhzada, modern examples of wise words in his works created and made a modern contribution to the development of the Uzbek literary language. Most of their own is used in everyday conversation due to its charming and charming word choice. Aphorisms found in common phrases as well as popular literature.

CONCLUSION

Studying the above aphorisms is advice, guidance or allows you to get advice, vital conclusions. In general, each is wise the word is an expression of folk wisdom, a summation of many years of life experience. The appearance of wise words in the language is determined by the history of the people who created them. Many aphorisms were created in ancient times and are still their creators lives with people who are Aphorisms are popular and passed down from generation to generation, lives for centuries. In the process of scientific research, most aphorisms are two at the same time meaning: we have also determined that it includes a direct and figurative meaning, that's why we sometimes have a hard time understanding aphorisms at first glance. Basically, the figurative or implied meaning of aphorisms is usually a metaphor, through

expensive devices such as metonymy, hyperbole, simile or metaphor delivered. The aphorism is indispensable for the next generation. Who read these aphorisms if he understands, he will be perfect in every way.

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